

Synthesis of Possible Antifertility Compounds: Part I. Synthesis of 4-*o*-Benzyl-2-Hydroxy Phenyl-*N*-Arylthiosemicarbazones

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Eight new thiosemicarbazones have been prepared by the condensation of 4-*o*-benzyl resacetophenone with *N*-aryl thiosemicarbazides with a view to test their antifertility activity.

A LARGE number of 4-(Substituted)-3 thiosemicarbazones¹ and 1-(*p*-dichloroacetamido-acetophenone)-3-thiosemicarbazones²⁻³ have been reported in recent years to possess powerful anti-spermatogenic activity. Prescott and Li⁴ demonstrated the thiosemicarbazones to possess low toxicity. Therefore, it was worthwhile to prepare a few compounds of 4-*o*-benzyl-2-hydroxy-phenyl-*N*-aryl-thiosemicarbazone series, which appear to be the potent contraceptives. The synthesis was accomplished along the following route (Scheme I).

Migration of acetyl group takes place in compound (II) when reacted with benzyl chloride⁵.

In compound II the acetylation of *p*-hydroxy group is preferential than *o*-hydroxy group to -COCH₃ group's position as the latter one suffers from steric hindrance.

The structure given in compound V is supported by infrared spectroscopy as the peaks of all vital functional groups tally with the standard values

reported in the literature. Absorption frequencies for -OH, -C = N and -C = S groups are observed at 3550 ~ 3200 cm⁻¹, 1689 ~ 1471 cm⁻¹ and 1250 ~ 1020 cm⁻¹, respectively. In the i.r. spectra of all the compounds listed in Table 1, the peaks for the above functional groups appear nearly at 3250 cm⁻¹, 1500 cm⁻¹ and 1138 cm⁻¹ respectively.

The preliminary testing of these compounds reveals their positive antifertility activity. To study their potentiality and exact mode of action their screening is being done, which shall be reported in our next publication.

Experimental

Preparation of resacetophenone (I)

This was prepared by the established method⁶.

Preparation of *N*-aryl-thiosemicarbazides :

This was synthesized according to the method of Sen and Gupta⁷.

Preparation of 4-acetyl resacetophenone (II) :

1 ml of pyridine was added to a suspension of 6.08 g (0.04 M) of resacetophenone in 14 ml (0.04M) of acetic anhydride. The resultant mixture was warmed and after 5 min, 100 ml of water was added to this. The solid which appeared after a few minutes was filtered and recrystallised from methanol. Colourless needles, m.p. 75° (lit. 76°).

Preparation of 4-*o*-benzyl-2-acetyl-resacetophenone (III) :

A mixture of 3.88 g (0.02M) of 4-acetyl-resacetophenone 2.5 g (0.02M) of benzyl chloride, 0.25 g. of potassium iodide and 5 g of anhydrous potassium carbonate in 50 ml of anhydrous acetone was refluxed for 5 hr. The mixture was cooled, filtered and acetone was removed by distillation. The pasty mass, thus obtained, was dissolved in boiling cyclohexane. On cooling, colourless solid mass separated out. It was filtered and recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 109° (lit. 111°-12°)⁵.

4-*o*-Benzyl-resacetophenone (IV) :

2 g (0.01M) of 4-*o*-benzyl-2-acetyl-resacetophenone was hydrolysed by adding 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution to its solution in boiling methanol (10 ml). After 5 min. the solution was cooled, diluted with water and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The solid thus obtained was filtered and recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 103° (lit. 104°).⁵

Preparation of 4-*o*-benzyl-2-hydroxyphenyl-*N*-aryl-thiosemicarbazones (V) :

In a 100 ml r.b. flask fitted with a reflux condenser and calcium chloride guard tube, a mixture of 4-*o*-benzyl-resacetophenone (0.005M) and arylthiosemicarbazide (0.005M) in 10 ml of absolute ethanol and

two drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid, was refluxed for 4 hrs. Subsequently ethanol was removed by distillation and the solid obtained, was recrystallised from ethanol. All the compounds thus reported are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—4-*o*-BENZYL-2-HYDROXY PHENYL-*N*-ARYL THIOSEMICARBAZONE

R	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis of Nitrogen	
			Calcd.	Found
1 Phenyl	220	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ S	10.7	9.97
2 <i>p</i> -Tolyl	210	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	10.3	10.10
3 Cyclohexyl	185	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	10.5	10.48
4 <i>o</i> -Tolyl	225	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	10.3	9.87
5 <i>o</i> -Methoxy	220	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	9.97	9.58
6 <i>p</i> -Ethoxy	223	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	9.6	9.24
7 <i>o</i> -Ethoxy	234	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	9.6	9.75
8 <i>p</i> -Methoxy	236	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	9.97	9.56

Note : Melting points are uncorrected. The percent yield ranges from 50 to 60%. Solvent used for recrystallisation is ethanol.

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